

EFFICIENCY OF TEACHING ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE PROJECTS

Kasimjanova Hamidahon Botirjon qizi

Andijan State University, Faculty of Physics and Mathematics,
3rd year student of Physics

Rahmonkulova Nargiza Bahramjon qizi

Andijan State University, Faculty of Physics and Mathematics,
3rd year student of Physics

Abdumannapova Madinabonu Fazliddin qizi

Andijan State University Pedagogical Institute Technological
Education 1st year student

Abstract: *This article describes the practice of innovative activities and best pedagogical practices and the history of their origin. In addition, V.A. Slasten's acmeological approach to the creation of innovative activities of the teacher is analyzed.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, innovation, aspect, concept, professionalism, individuality, acmeology, creativity.*

Innovation is derived from the English word "innovation", which means "innovation", "innovation". The development of modern education has created a new direction - innovative pedagogy. This term was studied in Western Europe and the United States in the 60s of the last century in the works of G. N. Gonobolin, S. M. Godnin, V. M. Zagvyazinsky, V. A. Kan-Kalik. The work of H. Barnet, J. Basset, D. Hamilton analyzes the management of innovation processes, the organization of change in education, the conditions necessary for the "life and activity" of innovation [1].

The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American E. Rodgers. Scientists distinguish between two approaches to studying the components of innovation processes. Individual micro-levels of news and micro-levels of interactions entered separately. The first approach highlights an idea that has been put into practice. The second approach is the interaction of innovations

introduced separately, their existence, competition, and the consequent replacement of one by the other.

The literature on innovative pedagogy shows that the innovation process includes the following stages.

1. The stage of birth of a new idea or concept of innovation. It is also called the discovery phase;
2. The stage of invention. Innovation creation phase;
3. The stage of implementation of the created innovation;
4. Dissemination of innovation, the stage of its widespread implementation;
5. The dominant stage of innovation in a particular field. At this stage, the novelty loses its novelty. There is a viable alternative;
6. The stage of reducing the scope of the innovation by replacing it on the basis of a new alternative.

The concept of "new" is central to pedagogical innovation. There is also an interest in private, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogy. The private novelty, according to V.A. Slastenin, involves the renewal of one of the elements of a particular system product in the current modernization. The set of specific elements that lead to a complex and progressive update is called conditional innovation. Local innovation is defined by the use of innovation in a particular facility. Subjective novelty is defined as the fact that the object itself is new for a particular object [2].

R.N Yusufbekova considers pedagogical novelty in teaching and upbringing as a previously unknown and previously unnoticed situation, the changing content of pedagogical reality, which leads to the development of theory and practice. In pedagogical innovation RN Yusufbekova distinguishes three blocks of the structure of the innovation process.

The first block is the block of new separation in pedagogy. These include the classification of innovations in pedagogy, the conditions for the creation of innovations, the norms of innovation, the readiness of innovations to master and use them, traditions and innovations, the stages of innovation in pedagogy.

The second block is the block of new perception, mastering and evaluation, pedagogical communities, the diversity of the process of new assessment and mastering, the environment of conservatism and innovation in pedagogy, the readiness of pedagogical societies to understand and evaluate new.

The third block is the block of new use and introduction, that is, the laws and types of introduction, use and widespread introduction of new. Innovative activity of a teacher is considered as a result of creative process and creative activity. V.A. Slastenin takes an acmeological approach to the creation of innovative activities of the teacher. "Acme" is a Greek word meaning high point, sharp, flourishing, mature, the best period, and this field is called acmeology. VA Ananov, NV Kuzmina, AA Dechkach and others think about the most creative periods of human life, the stages of maturity, which are accompanied by increasing the effectiveness of professional activity [3]. They deal with the professionalism of mature people, the mental laws of the heyday of personal development, the ability to overcome the peaks of professionalism. V.A. Slastenin substantiates the subjective and objective factors of acmeology that lead to high professionalism, longevity of the specialist. Objective factors include the quality of education, and subjective factors include a person's talents and abilities, and responsibility for effectively solving production tasks.

Factors for achieving high professionalism are: talent, ability, education, family upbringing, conditions, school, self-discipline. Acmeology is viewed from a scientific point of view in a relationship of professionalism and creativity. The following categories are distinguished: creative individuality, the process of self-growth and improvement, creative experience as the realization of their potential. The creative individuality of the teacher includes: Intellectual-creative initiative, breadth and depth of knowledge, alertness to contradictions, critical approach to creativity, ability to fight for creativity, thirst for information, a sense of unusualness and innovation in problems, professionalism , thirst for knowledge. The acmeological approach in the analysis of the structure of innovative activity allows

to reveal the laws of personal development of the teacher in achieving the peaks of professionalism.

The most important characteristic of a teacher's innovative activity is creativity. The term creativity originated in Anglo-American psychology in the 1960s and refers to the ability to create new concepts and new skills. J.Gilford shows a number of individual abilities that characterize creativity: fluency of thought, originality, curiosity, the ability to make assumptions, imagination, fantasy (fantasy). offers. In his view, potential creativity is a creative activity that represents the location of the individual, which is theoretically ready to become active in certain external conditions. Potential creativity is a necessary subjective condition of creativity. Creativity in action is creativity that provides direct preparation for a type of creative activity. Active creativity is the most important subjective condition of creativity [4]. The analysis of teacher innovation requires the use of certain criteria that determine the effectiveness of innovation. Such standards include novelty, acceptability, high efficiency, and the ability to creatively apply innovation to mass experiments. Pedagogical innovation must, by its very nature, be the property of mass experimentation. Pedagogy first brings innovation to the work of individual teachers. At the next stage, after testing and objective assessment, it is recommended to implement it as a pedagogical innovation. The teacher's innovative activities include analyzing and evaluating innovation, formulating goals and concepts for future actions, implementing and editing this plan, and evaluating effectiveness. The most important thing in innovation is the personality of the teacher. The teacher must be an innovator, a productive creative person, with a broad interest in creativity and a rich inner world, revenge for pedagogical innovation. The study of innovative processes, development laws, mechanisms and implementation technologies allows to organize the educational process at the level of world standards based on the achievements of modern pedagogy and psychology.

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